

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

Volume I Issue VI

ECHOES *of* EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

OCTOBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Volume I Issue VI

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VI (October 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

ROY B. GACUS, PhD

College Research Coordinator

University of Southern Mindanao

Bai Matabai Plang Ave., Poblacion, Kabacan,

Cotabato Province, Philippines

[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17257477](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17257477)

Walay Perpekto

Dili tanang buotan maayo,
og dili tanang maayo buotan.

Dili tanang utukon hawod,
og dili tanang hawod utokon.

Dili tanang kwartahan kabalo mobasa,
og dili tanang kabalo mobasa kwartahan.

Dili tanang lider politiko,
og dili tanang politiko lider.

Dili tanang limpyado matarong,
og dili tanang matarong limpyado.

Dili tanang himsog malungtaron,
og dili tanang malungtaron himsog.

Labaw sa tanan, dili tanang relihiyoso malangit,
og dili tanang malangit relihiyoso.

Busa walay tawo nga perpekto,
kay bisan ang kalibutan dili perpekto.